

Covid-19

by Dimitar Kovatchev, D-r (BG)

Western medicine's confrontation with the virus has brought new surprising facts to the fore, which have not yet been scientifically summarized, and has given birth to a potential "Klondike" for discoveries. As a general practitioner, who is close to the immediate treatment of Covid-19 sufferers, I was granted a few months for "dry" thinking exercises. I would take the liberty of sharing some facts and conclusions about the virus that differ from those generally known.

The disease is an invention of a viral nature in the respiratory tract, which in most cases runs with the expected characteristics. Here everything is known as with influenza infection.

However, Covid-19 can also develop into another form, which proceeds with shortness of breath and severe complications. Namely this development of the disease is the subject of my thoughts since the last weeks.

By this form we must exclude the pre-existing conditions (oncological and cardiological diseases, diabetes, COPD), which cause a severe course and mortality. We must also rule out the bacterial complications that are known from other types of virus and are treated by antibiotics and symptomatic agents, the enemy of which both the immunity and the doctors know well. The cases cleared of these well-known "conditions", which surprisingly become dangerously complicated by respiratory distress and organ deterioration, sometimes develop in age groups with expected stable immunity.

The emerging difference is the significant lack of oxygen in nonsuppurative and tumor-free airways, the deficit of serious bronchospasm and the ineffectiveness of bronchodilators.

It is obvious that the air reaches the alveoli, but from there the oxygen cannot be further delivered to the necessary organs. There are two possibilities for this to happen:

1. if the blood does not flow properly through the alveoli /microembolism, blood clotting in the alveolar micro-vessels/;
2. if the oxygen-carrying haemoglobin is destroyed /the haem is destroyed and releases iron/.

The scientists quickly noticed signs of the presence of both processes in the development of the disease, about which the following relations can be made:

In 2004, while working on the cell death programme, Brinkmann discovered the so-called NETS /neutrophilic extracellular traps/. These traps are full of granulocytes that contain enzymes such as myeloperoxidase /MPO/, neutrophil elastase /NE/ and others.

The new virus apparently causes the formation of such traps from neutrophils /white blood cells, the value of which is unexpectedly high by Covid-19, and is usually not increased by the viral infections known so far/, from the granulocytes the enzymes MPO and NE are released, one of which damages the haemoglobin and is responsible for the increase of coagulation and the blockage of the micro-vessels, and the other is more responsible for the fibrous changes that occur later.

If we accept this hypothesis, every patient should be considered as one who will at any moment have a pulmonary embolism /even though of the micro-vessels/.

Embolism is a disease whose mortality and recovery rates, as well as age groups affected, are very similar to Covid-19's own, where it rarely affects or injures children. The treatment of this aggravation is well known and is already widely used. I believe that the emphasis should be placed on prevention.

The same damage mechanism turns the infected persons into patients with potentially damaged hemoglobin /radiographs with existing hemosiderosis, elevated ferritin, originally compensatory elevated and later low hemoglobin/. Since the enzyme MPO is responsible for the destruction of hemoglobin and its haem, causing the detachment of iron and its accumulation in the lungs and other organs, attention should be focused on MPO and its inhibition.

Such drugs are:

- Retrovir - anti-HIV drug, registered in Bulgaria;
- Isoniazid - antituberculosis drug;
- the Statins - lipid reducers;
- Antioxidants - vitamin C, Ambroxol and others;
- Chlorogenic acid - esters of caffeic and quinic acid (contained in coffee and dicotyledonous seeds), which may be related to quinine;
- **Quercetin** - a substance that should be generally considered as the most harmless, effective and cheap, and is clinically proven as an inhibitor of MPO. It is contained in many foods and is available in free sale, including in Bulgaria;

The neutrophil elastase suppressing drugs are unfortunately few:

- Elaspol, which is not available in Bulgaria;
- Azithromycin, already widely known;
- Fenofibrate, there is also a Bulgarian product;
- Alpha-1-antitrypsin recombinant, complicated application.

From all of the above, the following questions arise for me, to which we doctors must find the answers:

1. Shouldn't the Antimyeloperoxidase test /antiMPO, 28 BGN/ be taken into account and introduced into the examinations of the patients, and at what stage should this be done?

2. How early should D-dimer, ferritin, troponin, calcitonin, CRP and the mentioned MPO be listed in the diagnostic scheme of the infected persons and at what values should be started with immediate anticoagulant treatment and Quercetin?

3. Shouldn't one have to consider as a preventive measure in some initial cases the Antistenocardin /dipyridamole/ - a cheap Bulgarian drug /contraindicated only in patients with known coagulation problems and those who take anticoagulants or tend to bleed/, which has already been reported by the Chinese experts as a successful remedy in empirical cases in the chaos of the first outbreak, whose in vitro effectiveness against Covid-19 has been confirmed? This can be used, after medical advice of course, because of its antiviral effect, antuocoagulant efficiency and the increase of natural interferon

[/https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339597445_Therapeutic_effects_of_dipyridamole_on_COVID-19_patients_with_coagulation_dysfunction/](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339597445_Therapeutic_effects_of_dipyridamole_on_COVID-19_patients_with_coagulation_dysfunction/).

4. Wouldn't it be necessary to clarify the role of peripheral doctors in differentiating between mild or potential high-risk patients before the disease spreads massively, and with which markers should this be done? Will we continue to wait until someone suffocates to send him to the hospital?

5. Could it be, if we conditionally assume the severe cases as microembolism, that the genetic predisposition 4G/4G and 4G/5G is related to the severity of the disease? The examination with PAI1 can be done in any laboratory, but the relation with whether the hospitalized patients belong to this group can only be seen by doctors fighting for life in clinical isolation, and they probably do not have time to identify specific genes of their patients /without examination these would be women who have undergone pre-eclampsia prevention during pregnancy/. The recessive variant for such a genetic predisposition is about ten percent in Bulgaria.

Used sources:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/neuroscience/chlorogenic-acid>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2078229/>
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cathepsin_S
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3079352/>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3079352/>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3863628/>
<https://www.hindawi.com/journals/mi/2008/135625/>
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0003986117307725?via%3Dihub>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5665680/>
<https://www.longdom.org/open-access/sandwich-elisa-for-circulating-myeloperoxidase-and-neutrophil-elastasedna-complexes-released-from-neutrophil-extracellular-traps-2379-1764-1000196.pdf>
<https://books.google.bg/books?id=CSjvBwAAQBAJ&pg=PA355&lpg=PA355&dq=methimazole+inhibit+myeloperoxidase&source=bl&ots=aURPLxPXWc&sig=ACfU3U13KrLCctcdA9A-veQdwP7C0UK3Qw&hl=bg&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwi0rvu64fPoAhX0XxUIHaNIBf4Q6AEwBxoECAoQAQ#v=onepage&q=methimazole%20inhibit%20myeloperoxidase&f=false>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/2155713>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29708335>
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324857106_Inhibitive_Effects_of_Quercetin_on_Myeloperoxidase-Dependent_Hypochlorous_Acid_Formation_and_Vascular_Endothelial_Injury
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/3024872>
<https://www.cibalab.com/products-department.php>
<http://medicine-bg.net/mainmenu-39/3173-anti-neutrofilni-citoplazmeni-antitela-anca>
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/j.1538-7836.2011.04425.x>
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Neutrophil_elastase
https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/product-information/respreeza-epar-product-information_bg.pdf
https://www.puls.bg/reference/dictionary/dictionary_1913.html
<http://medicine-bg.net/mainmenu-39/3042-alfa-1-antitripsin>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/6961876>
<https://inspiro-bg.com/terapevtitchno-povliyavane-na-vazpalitelniya-protse-pri-hobb-v-nepokriti-nuzhdi-i-badeshti-predizvikatelstva/>
<https://apteka.framar.bg/21000295/%D1%84%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%BE%D1%84%D0%B8%D0%B1%D1%80%D0%B0%D1%82-%D0%BA%D0%B0%D0%BF%D1%81-100-%D0%BC%D0%B3-50>
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339597445_Therapeutic_effects_of_dipyridamole_on_COVID-19_patients_with_coagulation_dysfunction